

PRAGMALINGUISTICS AS AN AUTONOMOUS DOMAIN WITHIN LINGUISTIC THEORY

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Abstract: This article offers a theoretical overview of pragmalinguistics, focusing on the linguistic encoding of pragmatic meaning. It reviews the historical development of the science, key concepts such as speech acts, implicature, politeness theory, and the contributions of prominent scholars. The article also highlights the main tasks of investigation of pragmalinguistics, along with the role of pragmalinguistics in examining language use in context, providing a concise account of its central concepts and research focus.

Keywords:

Pragmalinguistics, speech acts, politeness, implicature, main tasks of investigation

Introduction

Understanding how language conveys meaning beyond the literal level has long been a central concern in linguistic research. Pragmalinguistics addresses this by examining the linguistic resources speakers use to express intentions and achieve communicative goals. Pragmalinguistics began to develop as an independent field in the 1960s and 1970s within the anthropocentric paradigm. During this period, traditional linguistic approaches, which were largely syntax-based, came under increasing criticism. Earlier frameworks assumed that a valid linguistic description had to be primarily syntactic in nature. However, such approaches proved insufficient for explaining how language functions in real-life communication. The "pragmatic turn" in linguistics thus can be described as a **shift from the paradigm of theoretical grammar to the paradigm centred on the language user [Mey,1993,2001]**. Pragmalinguistics is a subfield of linguistics that combines pragmatics and linguistics to investigate the relationship between language and its use in context. Several prominent scholars defined the term "pragmalinguistics". Leech introduced pragmalinguistics as "the study of the more linguistic end of pragmatics – where we consider the particular resources which a given language provides for conveying particular illocutions" [Leech, 1983] Jacob May describes "pragmatic linguistics (or pragmalinguistics) as the study of linguistic action as determined by the social conditions for speaking and understanding". As he claims, "from a pragmatic viewpoint, the conditions for speaking and understanding, for 'production' and 'consumption' of language, cannot be divorced from the conditions of production and consumption in the society in general" [Mey,1979].

J. Austin initiated the discipline by introducing the speech act theory in his work "How to do things with words"[1962]. Misinterpreting **illocutionary force is a major cause of pragmatic failure**. This theory was further elaborated by J.R. Searle in Speech Acts [1969] and Expression and Meaning [1979], where he classified speech act types and introduced "felicity conditions". Moreover, H.P. Grice made a great contribution to pragmalinguistics through his theory "Logic and Conversation" [1975], creating the Cooperative Principle and maxims. Violation of these maxims often leads to pragmatic failure, especially in a cross-cultural context. Later, G. Leech developed these ideas into a framework of pragmatic evaluation in Principles of Pragmatics [1983], in particular, through the Politeness Principle. Jenny Thomas differentiated Pragmalinguistic failures from Sociopragmatic failures in her work "Cross-cultural pragmatic

failure" [1983]. These contributions collectively demonstrate that pragmalinguistics is a multidirectional and interdisciplinary domain that combines philosophical speech act theory, cognitive inferential models, politeness and value evaluation systems, and anthropocentric cultural-linguistic perspectives.

The first prominent theory in the history of pragmalinguistics is the Speech Act Theory. It was introduced by J. Austin, and further developed by his pupil Searle. Misunderstandings of illocutionary force cause many communication failures. According to Searle, "speech act is the basic or minimal unit of communication" [Searle, 1969]. The main principles of Speech Act Theory are that the produced utterance is understood as an action within the framework of social institutions and conventions, saying is regarded as doing, words are deeds, and utterances are equal to actions

J. Austin distinguished three basic aspects of speech acts:

1. Locutionary act (what is said by the addresser)
2. Illocutionary act (what is meant by the speaker, the pragmatic intention)
3. Perlocutionary act (the effect of what is said on the addressee)

The theory of speech acts aims to do justice to the fact that even though words (phrases, sentences) encode information, people do more things with words than convey information, and that when people do convey information, they often convey more than their words encode.

Paul Grice proposed the "Conversational Implicature" theory, a foundational framework in pragmalinguistics, in his work "Logic and Conversation" in 1975. According to this, speakers convey implied meaning beyond the literal meanings of utterances by flouting, violating, opting out and suspending the Cooperative principle that consists of 4 maxims: Maxim of quantity (giving enough information, no more, no less), maxim of quality (providing truthful information), maxim of relevance (being on topic), and maxim of manner (being clear and brief) [Grice, 1975]. For example, "Some students came to class" implies "not all students came to class". Grice classified two types of implicature: conventional and conversational implicature. The former type of implicature is triggered by specific lexical items, not context-dependent, and cannot be cancelled without contradictions, while the latter is not tied to specific lexical units and depends on the conversational context, addressers' intentions, and Gricean maxims.

The main task of pragmalinguistics is to investigate the language in terms of its pragmalinguistic role. It examines the functional relationship between grammatical structures, lexical choices, prosody, and communicative intentions, classification of speech act types, and their linguistic realizations. Pragmatic markers and formulaic expressions that express indirectness, mitigation, politeness, and other interpersonal meanings in language are also considered as the main tasks of investigation of Pragmalinguistics. Moreover, it explores cross-cultural variations in the linguistics strategies that are applied to perform similar pragmatic functions in different languages. Thus, the core aim of pragmalinguistic investigation is to describe the linguistic means by which speakers generate pragmatic effects in communication. Finally, Pragmalinguistics plays a central role in examining the different types of communication in the real world in various contexts as it combines theoretical, social, and cognitive perspectives. As Thomas indicates, pragmatic failure is not only an academic concern; it actually mirrors communication breakdowns in everyday discourse [Thomas, 1995]. Therefore, pragmalinguistics helps to understand language use in context by providing the analytical framework

Conclusion

Pragmalinguistics provides a systematic framework for understanding how speakers encode pragmatic meaning within linguistic forms. This article has outlined the historical development of the field, highlighted key concepts such as speech acts, implicature, politeness, and conventionalized indirectness, and reviewed the contributions of prominent scholars. It has also discussed the main tasks of pragmalinguistic investigation. By consolidating these theoretical insights, the paper offers a coherent overview of pragmalinguistics, clarifying its central notions, research focus, and role in the study of linguistic meaning.

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